

Program Description of the Monte Carlo simulation

for the paper

*“Intrinsic volumes of the quantum state space and
mutually unbiased bases”*

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1 Purpose of the Program

This program estimates, via Monte Carlo (MC) simulation, the coefficients of the polynomial describing the volume of the ε -neighborhood of the *complementarity polytope* constructed from $(N + 1)$ mutually orthogonal N -vertex simplices in \mathbb{R}^{N^2-1} . Note that, in our paper, we use d in place of N , since it denotes the dimension of the original complex vector space \mathbb{C}^d . The main purpose of this program is to confirm our derived analytic formulas (Theorem 2 in the paper) to several decimal places, and the code may be useful to other researchers for estimating further intrinsic volumes.

2 Geometric Background

The *complementarity polytope* $\mathcal{P}_N \subset \mathbb{R}_1^{N-1} \oplus \dots \oplus \mathbb{R}_{N+1}^{N-1} \cong \mathbb{R}^{(N^2-1)}$ is defined as the convex hull of $N + 1$ mutually orthogonal $(N - 1)$ -simplices, each centered at the origin. Each of these simplices can be described by its N vertices (in the appropriate orthogonal subspace):

$$v_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -r_2 \\ -r_3 \\ -r_4 \\ \vdots \\ -r_N \end{bmatrix}, v_2 = \begin{bmatrix} R_2 \\ -r_3 \\ -r_4 \\ \vdots \\ -r_N \end{bmatrix}, v_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ R_3 \\ -r_4 \\ \vdots \\ -r_N \end{bmatrix}, \dots, v_{N-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ R_{N-1} \\ -r_N \end{bmatrix}, v_N = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ R_N \end{bmatrix}$$

where $r_N = 1/\sqrt{N(N-1)}$ and $R_N = \sqrt{(N-1)/N}$ denote the radii of the inscribed and circumscribed spheres, respectively.

Let $D = N^2 - 1$. Consider the ε -neighborhood $\mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon}$ of the complementarity polytope; i.e. the set of points of \mathbb{R}^D whose distance from \mathcal{P}_N is less than or equal to ε . It is well-known that the (D -dimensional) volume of $\mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon}$ is a polynomial of ε of order D :

$$\text{vol}_D(\mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon}) = C_D + C_{D-1}\varepsilon + C_{D-2}\varepsilon^2 + \dots + C_0\varepsilon^D.$$

The coefficients C_{D-k} correspond to the volume contributions of different orders in ε . Clearly, $C_D = \text{vol}_D(\mathcal{P}_N)$ is simply the volume of \mathcal{P}_N , and it is also not difficult to see that C_{D-1} is actually the surface area of \mathcal{P}_N . It turns out that the further coefficients are some

sort of measures of the “lower-dimensional contents” of the polytope. (In the paper, we use \tilde{V}_k in place of C_k , for historical reason.)

The main idea is not to measure the $\text{vol}_D(\mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon})$ itself (and then calculating the coefficients by differentiation or by fitting a polynomial), instead we can measure the coefficients directly, by decomposing the ε -neighborhood into a union of disjoint sets:

$$\mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon} = \bigcup_{k=0}^D R_{k,\varepsilon}, \quad R_{k,\varepsilon} := \{x \in \mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon} \mid \text{closest point of } \mathcal{P}_N \text{ to } x \text{ lies on the interior of a } k\text{-dimensional face}\}$$

for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, D$. The volumes of these disjoint sets are precisely the terms appear in the polynomial

$$\text{vol}_D(R_{D-k,\varepsilon}) = C_{D-k}\varepsilon^k \tag{1}$$

so the coefficients C_{D-k} can be estimated independently and directly by measuring the volumes of $R_{D-k,\varepsilon}$. Estimating the coefficients in this way is much more efficient.

Due to the high degree of symmetry in the construction, all facets (i.e., faces of dimension $D - 1 = N^2 - 2$) of \mathcal{P}_N are of the same type, up to coordinate permutations and orthogonal transformations. In particular, each facet is isometric to a specific facet F_{D-1} (whose vertices we will denote by a_1, \dots, a_D in Section 3). Each of its N^{N+1} facets corresponds to a non-regular N -dimensional simplex

$$F_D := \text{conv}(\{0\} \cup F_{D-1})$$

which are congruent and disjoint in volume. Thus, to find the volumes of $R_{D-k,\varepsilon}$ it is sufficient to measure the ε -neighborhoods which fall in the positive cone generated by F_D , that is

$$\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon} := R_{D-k,\varepsilon} \cap \{tv \mid v \in F_D, t \geq 0\} \quad \text{for } k = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, D \tag{2}$$

and then multiply the result by N^{N+1} .

3 Monte Carlo Method

3.1 Sample space

If the random points were generated in a box, then the volume (so the ε -neighborhood) of F_D would be too small compared to the volume of the containing box, that would make the MC inefficient. And this effect would even get worse as the dimension increases (for $N = 6$, the dimension of the embedding space is already $D = 35$). So the program uses the Dirichlet distribution, that is, it generates uniformly distributed random points within a larger simplex that tightly encloses the ε -neighborhoods $\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon}$. This larger simplex is called the *sample space*, which is obtained by scaling each simplex vertex vector by $(1 + \varepsilon/m)$,

$$K_{MC} := \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{m}\right) F_D, \quad m = \frac{1}{N} \left\| \sum_{i=1}^N v_i \right\|.$$

where m is the height of the simplex F_D (i.e., the distance of the facet F_{D-1} from the origin). It is not difficult to see that $\mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon} \subset K_{MC}$ (and the containment is tight in the sense that for any $\lambda < 1$: $\mathcal{P}_{N,\varepsilon} \not\subset \lambda K_{MC}$). This ensures the enclosing volume is efficient for MC sampling. The volume of K_{MC} is analytically known and equals

$$\text{vol}_D(K_{MC}) = \frac{\text{vol}_D(\mathcal{P}_N)}{N^{N+1}} (1 + \varepsilon/m)^D.$$

3.2 Brief Algorithm

Random points p in K_{MC} are generated as linear combinations of its $(N + 1)$ vertices using a normal Dirichlet distribution. For each $\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon}$ there is a corresponding counter which counts the random points that fall within $\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon}$. So each point (if it lies in the ε -neighborhood) is classified according to which of the $\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon}$ it belongs to, and the corresponding counter is incremented, that is: For each random point p , the closest point p_0 on the simplex F_D is found along with the dimension $D - k$ of the face F_{D-k} containing p_0 (the method of finding the closest point is discussed in the next subsection). If $|p - p_0| > \varepsilon$, then p is ignored as it lies outside the ε -neighborhood. If $|p - p_0| \leq \varepsilon$ holds, the appropriate counter is incremented.

3.3 Detailed Algorithm

New sample point p

First a Dirichlet distribution $(\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_D)$ is generated over the $(D + 1)$ vertices (a_0, a_1, \dots, a_D) of F_D where a_0 is the origin. Let

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_D)$$

be the next set of D Dirichlet coefficients without the coefficient corresponding to the origin. Define the barycentric weights:

$$w_i = \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon}{m}\right) \alpha_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, D.$$

With this notation $p = \sum_{i=1}^D w_i a_i$ is the generated random point in the sample space K_{MC} . If

$$\sum_{i=1}^D w_i \leq 1, \quad \left(\Leftrightarrow w_0 := 1 - \sum_{i=1}^D w_i \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow \text{all } w_i \geq 0 \right)$$

then $p \in F_D$, (that is, the closest point is $p_0 = p$), so the counter of $\tilde{R}_{D,\varepsilon}$ is incremented, and **go to New sample point**. Else, continue with:

Set $k = 1$.

Projection step

We attempt to project p onto the affine hull of the face

$$F_{D-k}$$

with vertices

$$a_1, \dots, a_{D-k+1}.$$

1. Translate the affine space

Define

$$u_i = a_{i+1} - a_1, \quad i = 1, \dots, D - k,$$

and

$$p' = p - a_1.$$

Let $V = [u_1 \ \dots \ u_{D-k}]$ the matrix formed by the column vectors of u_i .

2. Orthogonal projection onto the linear span of $\{u_1, \dots, u_{D-k}\}$

We seek $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{D-k}$ such that

$$p' - V\lambda$$

is orthogonal to $\text{span}(V)$. Thus

$$V^T(p' - V\lambda) = 0,$$

which yields

$$\lambda = (V^T V)^{-1} V^T p'.$$

3. Affine projection

The orthogonal projection of p onto the affine hull of F_{D-k} is

$$p_{\text{proj}} = V\lambda + a_1 = \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^{D-k} \lambda_i\right) a_1 + \sum_{i=1}^{D-k} \lambda_i a_{i+1}.$$

The coefficients of a_1, \dots, a_{D-k+1} in the above formula are exactly the barycentric coordinates of p_{proj} relative to the vertices of the face F_{D-k} .

4. Case analysis

Case 1: All barycentric coordinates are non-negative

That is

$$1 - \sum_{i=1}^{D-k} \lambda_i \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_i \geq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, D-k,$$

then $p_{\text{proj}} \in F_{D-k}$, therefore $p_0 = p_{\text{proj}}$.

- If $\|p_0 - p\| \leq \varepsilon$, increment the counter of $\tilde{R}_{D-k, \varepsilon}$.

Go to New sample point.

Case 2: Some barycentric coordinates are negative

Let the set of vertices with negative barycentric coordinates be

$$\{a_{i_1}, a_{i_2}, \dots\}.$$

Remove these vertices from the face and increase

$$k \leftarrow k + \#\{\text{removed vertices}\}.$$

Renumber the remaining vertices as

$$a_1, \dots, a_{D-k+1},$$

and repeat the **Projection step**.

Remark

Since k increases monotonically and $k \leq D$, eventually only a single vertex remains. In that case,

$$p_0 = a_1$$

is the closest point to p on the simplex F_D . Thus the algorithm always finds the closest point of the simplex to p .

4 Program Output

The program outputs the **native counter values** of each $\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon}$, and after scaling them appropriately it obtains the **coefficients** C_{D-k} , that is

$$\text{vol}_D(\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon}) = \frac{\#\text{points in } \tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon}}{\#\text{points in } K_{MC}} \text{vol}_D(K_{MC})$$

and

$$\text{vol}_D(R_{D-k,\varepsilon}) = N^{N+1} \text{vol}_D(\tilde{R}_{D-k,\varepsilon})$$

then using equation 1 it computes the coefficients C_{D-k} . The input and output data formats are explained in `commented_output.pdf`. In the `program_output.txt` file we can see outputs for $N = 2, \dots, 10$, which show that the numerical estimates confirm our derived formulas (Theorem 2 in the paper) to several decimal places across multiple dimensions. The value of ε can be adjusted via the input parameters. Examining the native counter values we can see that the volumes of $R_{D-k,\varepsilon}$ depend strongly on the value of ε , thus for higher dimensions, convergence may depend sensitively on the chosen ε .

5 Program Input

The input and output data formats are explained in `commented_output.pdf`. When executed without parameters, the program prints a usage reminder:

```
Usage: ./N_max_pw_eps_m_thread_e_frmt_lbuff_res_load_sqrt2.py N{2..13}
      n_points n_eps eps1 eps_N [seed(0:rnd) [amp_rnd_box [max_power_of_eps [x
      ]]]]
export SHOW_PRJ_MX=1 or unset SHOW_PRJ_MX to check simplex and projection
      matrices
export PATH_PRJ_MX=/path or unset PATH_PRJ_MX == ./ place of projection
      matrices
x stands for "don't resident"
```

Environment Variables

- `SHOW_PRJ_MX=1`: display simplex vertex vectors and projection matrices.
- `unset SHOW_PRJ_MX`: disable the above display.
- `PATH_PRJ_MX`: optional path to precomputed projection matrices (useful for slow hardware).

Additional Parameters

- `amp_rnd_box`: extra bias multiplier (default: 1).
- `max_power_of_eps`: limits the polynomial order to compute.
- `x`: if omitted, the program stays interactive after execution. Using the Up arrow we can recall the previous input line. The projection matrices are not recomputed (which is beneficial on slower hardware), although the parameters N and the `max_power_of_eps` cannot be changed.

6 Technical Information

- Language: Python 3.10+
- Required packages: `numpy`, `scipy`, `h5py`, `numba`
- OS: Linux (tested)
- Floating-point type: IEEE 754 double precision (`float64`)
- Performance: the critical functions are structured so that they can be compiled with `@njit` (Numba) and can make use of CPU multithreading.

Performance examples:

- AMD Ryzen 7 8700G (8C/16T, 4.2GHz): 20 million points for $N = 3$ in 1 second.
- AMD FX-6300 (6C/6T): 20 million points for $N = 3$ in about 10 seconds.

The file `ComplementaryPolytope_intrinsic_volumes_MC.py` contains the complete Python source code. The code is modular and extensively commented. Although the design focuses on computational efficiency, it also aims to emphasize mathematical transparency. The projection matrices are precomputed for efficiency and stored according to a combinatorial indexing scheme. The number of coefficients C_{D-k} is constrained by the chosen value of N , taking into account that the projection matrices must remain below 12 GB in size.